

Terpenoid constituents from some indigenous plants

Vivek Krishna, Sneha Sharma, R. B. Pareek and Pahup Singh*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, India

E-mail : pahupsingh@yahoo.co.uk

Manuscript received 2 April 2001, revised 11 September 2001, accepted 16 October 2001

Isolation of lupeol acetate, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, betulin, β -amyrin, lupeol, oleanolic acid from aerial parts and stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, β -amyrin, oleanolic acid from flowers of *Pyrostegia venusta*; β -sitosterol, friedelin, friedel-1-en-3-one, lupeol from heartwood of *Salmalia malabarica*; β -sitosterol, β -amyrin, epifriedelinol, oleanolic acid from heartwood of *Vitex negundo* and stigmasterol β -sitosterol, friedelin, betulinic acid from heartwood of *Punica granatum* have been reported.

Pyrostegia venusta C. B. Presl (Syn : *Bignonia venusta*) (Bignoniaceae) is one of the finest flowering climbers producing numerous drooping clusters of golden flowers from January to April and grows well in full sun on fence. *Salmalia malabarica* (Syn. *Bombax malabaricum*) (Bombacaceae), a tall deciduous tree, is distributed throughout hotter parts of India. *Vitex negundo* (Verbenaceae), an aromatic shrub, is widely distributed throughout India. *Punica granatum* Linn. (Punicaceae) is a spiny shrub or small tree and its fruits are used in diarrhoea and dysentery¹. *Salmalia* and *Vitex* species are well known for their medicinal importance in the indigenous system of treatment². A survey of literature revealed that no work has been done on aerial parts of *P. venusta*, however its flowers were investigated earlier³. Various parts of *S. malabarica*⁴, *V. negundo*⁵ and *P. granatum*⁶ have been chemically examined time to time. The present communication reports the isolation and characterization of lupeol acetate, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, betulin, β -amyrin, lupeol, oleanolic acid from aerial parts, and stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, β -amyrin, oleanolic acid from flowers of *P. venusta*; β -sitosterol, friedelin, friedel-1-en-3-one, lupeol from heartwood of *S. malabarica*; β -sitosterol, β -amyrin, epifriedelinol, oleanolic acid from heartwood of *V. negundo*, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, friedelin, betulinic acid from heartwood of *P. granatum* besides the previously reported compounds.

Results and Discussion

Constituents from aerial parts and flowers of P. venusta :

Lupeol acetate : Elution of column with petroleum ether afforded colourless needles (150 mg), m.p. 217–218°; gave positive Noller test for triterpenes; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1720 cm^{-1} ; m/z 468 [M^+] ($C_{32}H_{52}O_2$); $[\alpha]_D^{22}$ (CHCl_3); $^1\text{H NMR}$ δ 4.69 (s br, 4.57 (s br, = CH_2), 4.38 (dd, J 12, 5 Hz, H-3 α),

2.38 (m, H-19), 2.19 (s, OAc), 1.69 (s br, =C-Me), 0.76, 0.79, 0.83, 0.94, 0.97, 1.03 (all singlets, 6 \times Me); the identity was confirmed by its conversion to lupeol, m.p. 215–216°, on alkaline hydrolysis. *Stigmasterol* : Elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) gave colourless needles (500 mg), m.p. 166–167°; answered Liebermann-Burchard and Salkowski tests for sterols; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400 (OH), 1050 cm^{-1} (C–O); m/z 412 [M^+] ($C_{29}H_{48}O$); $^1\text{H NMR}$ δ 5.35 (t br, H-6), 5.12 (dd), 5.04 (dd, J 16, 10 Hz each H-22 and H-23), 3.50 (m, H-3 α), 1.09 (d, J 7 Hz, C-21 Me), 0.84 (t, J 7 Hz, C-29 Me), 0.70, 0.93, 1.16, 1.17 (4 \times Me); it was confirmed by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 144–145°. *β -Sitosterol* : Elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) gave colourless flakes (600 mg), m.p. 136–137°; gave positive Liebermann-Burchard colour reaction; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3410 (OH), 1050 cm^{-1} (C–O); m/z 414 [M^+] ($C_{29}H_{50}O$); $^1\text{H NMR}$ δ 5.3 (t br, H-6), 3.50 (m, H-3 α); the identification was assured by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 126–27°, and benzoate, m.p. 143–144°. *Betulin* : Elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) gave colourless crystals (120 mg), m.p. 254–256°; developed yellow colour with TNM for unsaturation and responded positively to Liebermann-Burchard and Noller tests; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3460–3400 (OH), 1650 cm^{-1} (C=C); m/z 442 [M^+] ($C_{30}H_{50}O_2$); $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ (Py); $^1\text{H NMR}$ δ 4.69 (s br), 4.57 (s br, = CH_2), 3.80 (d), 3.35 (d, J 11 Hz, each CH_2OH), 3.18 (dd, J 12, 5 Hz, H-3 α), 2.39 (m, H-19), 1.68 (s br, =C-Me), 0.75, 0.82, 0.96, 0.97, 1.02 (all singlets, 5 \times Me); it was characterized by preparation of its diacetate, m.p. 218–220° and dibenzoate, m.p. 179–180°. *β -Amyrin* : Elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 4) yielded colourless needles (200 mg), m.p. 196–197°; answered Noller test; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3380 (OH), 1650, 1050 cm^{-1} ; m/z

Note

426 [M⁺] (C₃₀H₅₀O); [α]_D + 87° (CHCl₃); ¹H NMR δ 3.19 (dd, *J* 12, 5 Hz, H-3α), 5.18 (t, *J* 7 Hz, H-12), 0.83 (s, Me), 0.87 (s, 4 × Me), 0.96 (s, 2 × Me), 1.13 (s, Me); its identity was confirmed by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 238–239°, and benzoate, m.p. 227–228°. *Lupeol*: Fraction obtained by eluting column with benzene afforded colourless needles (250 mg), m.p. 215–216°; responded positively to all colour reactions of triterpenes; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3640 (OH), 1640, 1040 cm⁻¹; *m/z* 426 [M⁺] (C₃₀H₅₀O); [α]_D + 27° (CHCl₃); ¹H NMR δ 4.65 (s br), 4.53 (s br, =CH₂), 3.19 (dd, *J* 12, 5 Hz, H-3α), 2.39 (m, H-19), 1.68 (s br, =C–Me), 0.76, 0.77, 0.81, 0.85, 0.93, 0.95 (all singlets, 6 × Me); it was identified as lupeol by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 217–218°. *Oleanolic acid*: Elution of column with benzene-ethylacetate (1 : 1) gave white needles (100 mg), m.p. 308–309°; responded Noller test for triterpenes; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3420–3100, 1700 cm⁻¹ (COOH); *m/z* 456 [M⁺] (C₃₀H₄₈O₃); [α]_D + 77.5° (CHCl₃); its conversion to methyl ester with ethereal solution of diazomethane further confirmed its identity: m.p. 199–200°; ¹H NMR δ 5.27 (t, *J* 7 Hz, H-12), 3.60 (s, OMe), 0.75 (s, Me), 0.80 (s, Me), 0.92 (s, 3 × Me), 1.00 (s, Me), 1.14 (s, Me).

The concentrated extract of its flowers on column chromatography gave stigmasterol (100 mg), β-sitosterol (80 mg), β-amyirin (120 mg) and oleanolic acid (40 mg) by eluting the same solvent system as described above.

Constituents from heartwood of *S. malabarica*:

Fractions obtained by eluting column with petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) and benzene (100%) afforded β-sitosterol (150 mg) and lupeol (70 mg), respectively. *Friedelin*: Elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) gave colourless needles (15 mg), m.p. 263–265°; answered Noller colour test for triterpenes; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1720 cm⁻¹; *m/z* 426 [M⁺] (C₃₀H₅₀O); [α]_D -25° (CHCl₃); ¹H NMR δ 0.88 (d, *J* 7 Hz, Me), 0.73 (s, Me), 0.88 (s, Me), 0.97 (s, Me), 1.01 (s, 2 × Me), 1.05 (s, Me), 1.18 (s, Me); the identity was confirmed by preparation of its oxime, m.p. 290–291°. *Friedel-1-en-3-one*: Elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) gave light yellow solid (130 mg), which on crystallization from benzene afforded colourless needles, m.p. 228–229°; answered Liebermann-Burchard and Noller tests; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1685 cm⁻¹ (C=C–C=O); [α]_D -73° (CHCl₃); *m/z* 424 [M⁺] (C₃₀H₄₈O); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 230 nm; the identification was confirmed by co-IR and m.m.p. with an authentic sample.

Constituents from heartwood of *V. negundo*:

Elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1), petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 4); benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) gave β-sitosterol (150 mg), β-amyirin (80 mg) and oleanolic acid (60 mg), respectively. *Epifriedelinol*: Fraction ob-

tained by eluting column with benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) afforded light yellow solid (135 mg), crystallized from benzene as shining flakes, m.p. 278–279°; gave positive Salkowski and Noller tests; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3490 cm⁻¹ (OH); *m/z* 428 [M⁺] (C₃₀H₅₂O); [α]_D +23° (CHCl₃); ¹H NMR δ 0.81 (d, *J* 7 Hz, Me), 0.86 (s, Me), 0.93 (s, Me), 0.94 (s, Me), 1.00 (s, 3 × Me), 1.17 (s, Me), 3.31 (m, H-3); prepared acetate, m.p. 290–291°; was identified as epifriedelinol from its spectral and chemical data.

Constituents of heartwood of *P. granatum*:

Fractions collected after elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1), petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) and petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) yielded stigmasterol (125 mg), β-sitosterol (100 mg) and friedelin (150 mg), respectively. *Betulinic acid*: Elution of column with benzene-ethylacetate (1 : 1) afforded colourless needles (200 mg), m.p. 316–317°; gave all colour reactions of triterpenes; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3325–2800, 1720 cm⁻¹ (COOH); *m/z* 456 [M⁺] (C₃₀H₄₈O₃); its conversion to methyl ester, m.p. 220–221° with ethereal solution of diazomethane confirmed its identity; methyl betulinate δ 4.60 (s br), 4.74 (s br, =CH₂), 3.68 (s, OMe), 3.18 (dd, *J* 12, 5 Hz, H-3α), 0.76 (s, Me), 0.82 (s, Me), 0.92 (s, Me), 0.97 (s, 2 × Me), 1.69 (s br, =C–Me), [α]_D +4° (CHCl₃).

Experimental

Aerial parts and flowers of *P. venusta* were procured from Botanical garden, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, while stem heartwoods of *S. malabarica*, *V. negundo* and *P. granatum* were collected from forests of Kota and Chittorgarh divisions of Rajasthan, and were identified with the help of RUBL, Herbarium, Jaipur.

The air-dried and coarsely powdered aerial parts (5 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether and flowers (2 kg) with chloroform of *P. venusta* and air-dried heart woods (4 kg) with acetone of *S. malabarica*, (3 kg) with petroleum ether of *V. negundo*, (3 kg) with petroleum ether of *P. granatum* on water-bath of 3 × 12 h. The extracts were concentrated separately under reduced pressure. Concentrated extracts were fractionated over Brockmann alumina (deactivated with 10% aqueous glacial acetic acid) using petroleum ether, petroleum ether-benzene mixtures (9 : 1, 4 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 4), benzene, benzene-ethyl acetate mixtures (4 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 4), ethyl acetate and methanol solvent system. Each fraction was further purified by crystallization and prep-TLC using Kiesel gel PF₂₅₄, 60 F₂₅₄ (Merck) plates.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head of the Department for facilities and to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. H. Santapau and A. N. Henry, "A Dictionary of the Flowering Plants in India", NISCOM. CSIR, 1998, p. 142.
2. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", 1975, Vol. 1, p. 357; S. K. Jain and R. A. Defillips, "Medicinal Plants of India", Reference Publications, 1995, Vol. 1, p. 191; B. N. Sastri in "The Wealth of India, Raw Materials", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1976, Vol. X, p. 524.
3. R. C. Dubey and K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 378.
4. J. Mukherjee and B. Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 769; D. N. Dhar and R. C. Munjal, *Planta Medica*, 1976, **29**, 148; V. Seshadri, A. K. Batta and S. Rangaswami, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14**, 616; G. S. Niranjana and P. C. Gupta, *Planta Medica*, 1973, **24**, 196; A. V. B. Sankaram, N. S. Reddy and J. N. Shoolery, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, **20**, 1877.
5. S. P. Vishnoi, A. Shoeb, R. S. Kapil and S. P. Popli, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 597; S. K. Bhargava, *Planta Medica*, 1964, **18**, 74; J. Banerji, B. Das, R. Chakraborty and H. Jha, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 597; J. A. Ferdous, A. Jabbar, M. Hassan and J. Choudhary, *J. Bangladesh Acad. Sci.*, 1984, **8**, 23; A. S. Chawla, A. K. Sharma, S. S. Handa and K. L. Dhar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, **30**, 773; S. Chandra and S. Babber, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, **26**, 82; A. S. Chawla, A. K. Sharma, S. S. Handa and K. L. Dhar, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1992, **55**, 163.
6. J. P. Wibaut, H. C. Beyerman and U. Hollsterin, *Konink. Ned. Akad. Wetenschap Proc. B*, 1955, **58**, 56 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1955, 10583); H. Neuhoefler, L. Witte, M. Gorunvic and F. C. Czygen, *Pharmazie*, 1993, **48**, 389; R. N. Chopra, I. C. Chopra and B. S. Verma, "Supplement to Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", NISCOM, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, Reprinted 1998, p. 84, and references therein; W. Mayer, A. Gomer and C. Andra, *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1977, 1976; T. Okuda, T. Yoshida, K. Mori and T. Holano, *Heterocycles*, 1981, **15**, 123; O. T. Schmidt, J. N. Schmidt and J. Herok, *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1954, **67**, 587; T. Okuda, T. Yoshida, N. Asida and K. Youki, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1983, 1765; O. T. Schmidt, W. Ebert and M. Wopp, *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1969, **729**, 251; N. Nishizawa, T. Yanuagishi, G. Nonaka and I. Mishioka, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1982, 2963; A. Haddock, R. K. Gupta, S. M. Atshaji and E. Haslam, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1982, 2515; O. T. Schmidt, R. Eckert, E. Gunther and H. Hesser, *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1967, **706**, 204; G. Noaka, I. Mishioka, T. Nagasawa and H. Oura, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1981, **29**, 2862; G. Nonaka, R. Sakai and I. Nishioka, *Phytochemistry*, 1984, **23**, 1753; M. A. M. Nawwar and A. M. F. Souleman, *Phytochemistry*, 1984, **23**, 2966; M. A. M. Nawwar, S. A. M. Hussein and I. Merfort, *Phytochemistry*, 1994, **36**, 993.